

DIDACTIC FOUNDATIONS OF COMPUTER EDUCATION IN THE TRAINING OF BIOLOGY TEACHERS

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Annotation. Computerization of Education provides for the mass application of certain methodological methods, standardizing the conditions of education, and as a result, the need arises to develop a new description of the laws on the legality of education, taking into account the deterministic relationship between the conditions of education and its results.

Keywords: Multimedia, computers, parameter informatization, dynamic, motivational.

As soon as the first computers appeared in educational institutions, a new direction in pedagogy was formed. This is education based on computer technologies. The author of this work conducted a number of studies on the psychological and pedagogical features of computer education. This section of our research is devoted to the analysis of the results of research conducted on this issue.

Most of the pedagogical research is devoted to the analysis of the advantages and effectiveness of computer-based education.

A computer is "a combination of a number of advantages - rapid learning, programmability, development, flexibility, integration, comprehensiveness, excellence." Also, "the computer is a technical tool that is absolutely compatible with its field of application of education, and it creates ample opportunities for the implementation of an active approach at all stages of the educational process." And again, "programming of the computer, in coordination with its dynamic flexibility, preserves the popularity and integrity of educational processes, and at the same time ensures its individuality."

The use of computers creates a basis for students' conscious perception of educational activities, increases the intellectual and logical level of the educational process, but can also cause a decrease in motivation in education.

Computer-based education has been widely used since the 80s of the last century and has been developing steadily. Due to its multifunctionality and wide possibilities, the computer is effectively used in teaching many subjects, including in the teaching of subjects included in the complex of biology.

To introduce computer education, it is not required to change the traditional model of pedagogical sciences. However, it is necessary to supplement the didactic principles in mastering pedagogical subjects. The form, method,

appearance and technologies of teaching in computer education change in a positive sense, that is, the computer does not suppress didactic principles, but enriches them and increases their absorbability. As a result of dialogic and visual training of students, it has a positive effect on the motivational environment of educational processes. The computerization of education standardizes the conditions of education, ensures the mass use of certain methodological methods, and as a result, develops a new description of the laws of the laws of education, taking into account the deterministic relationship between the conditions of education and its results. the need arises.

In order to achieve the necessary results in the computerization of education, it is as important to overcome computer addiction as it is to improve computer education. In the 21st century, it is necessary to abandon the narrow pragmatic approach regarding the computer as a didactic tool for teaching traditional subjects, and approach this tool in a broader sense. In particular, it should be considered as a means to change not only the form of education, but also its content, goals and objectives, objects of the educational system. It is only from this point of view that the use of computers in computer-based education is justified in terms of effectiveness. In the initial views, the trend of "saving educational time by implementing many processes in a short time as a result of computerization of education" did not justify itself. Modern approaches to education have shown that time planning is a stable and conservative parameter in improving the quality of teaching.

It should not be forgotten that there is still no universally recognized psychological-pedagogical theory of computer education, so computer programs are created without taking into account the principles of education. In our opinion, our national education system has accumulated enough experience in the field of computer software development, and we are experiencing a period of stability in computer education. This indicates that computer-based educational programs have not been proven to be more effective. That is, the computer programs that were considered new in a certain period of time soon become obsolete, and the desire to create new programs is correspondingly fading.

One of our goals in this work is to summarize the current state of computer education and try to analyze the main trends in computer education technologies.

Informatization on a global scale did not affect the teaching of biology in secondary schools. This, in turn, created the need to develop and put into

practice the teaching-methodical base of biology teaching based on new information technologies.

The processes of informatization of biology teaching require revision of the content of education and its educational and methodological base. For this, first of all, it is necessary to prepare teachers to work in new educational conditions. A number of educational subjects have been introduced in pedagogical higher educational institutions that allow future teachers to acquire new knowledge and skills in the field of using computer technology. The research conducted by the author of this work in the field of the use of information technology by biology teachers showed that the preparation of biology teachers for the introduction of new technologies in educational processes cannot be considered sufficient.

In order to positively solve the problem of effective use of information technologies in educational processes, it is necessary to have experience bases and a large number of biology teachers who effectively use these technologies in their practical activities.

Multimedia technology is one of the most advanced and at the same time rapidly developing technologies in the field of education. One of the advantages of this technology is that it expands the possibilities of summarizing information in different forms (for example, text, sound, image, photo, dynamic and static images) in the educational material. According to experts, this type of technology is very necessary, first of all, for general education schools, because it is in schools that students' professional interests are revealed and the foundation of knowledge in a specific field that will be developed in higher education institutions in the future is laid.

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